

The Relationship Between The Attitudes Of Faculty Members At King Abdulaziz University Towards Students With Learning Disabilities And Their Knowledge Of Their Characteristics

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 13, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: July 14, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Faculty Members, Learning Difficulties, Attitudes, Characteristics Of Students With Learning Disabilities</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8147604</p>	<p><i>The current study aimed to identify the relationship between the attitudes of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University towards students with learning difficulties and their knowledge of their characteristics. The current study relied on the descriptive correlational approach due to its suitability to the nature of the study. The study tool represented in the questionnaire - prepared by the two researchers - was applied to the study sample that was randomly selected for the study population, which numbered (122) from various faculty members at King Abdulaziz University. The results of the study showed that the level of attitudes of faculty members at King Abdul Aziz University towards students with learning difficulties was moderate. The level of their knowledge of the characteristics of students with learning difficulties was "high" on the total score and on all aspects of the dimension, and the existence of a statistically significant correlation at the level of significance between the level of attitudes of faculty members, and the axes of their level of knowledge of the characteristics of students with learning difficulties. The study also came out with the following recommendations: Researching using additional variables such as the source of knowledge about people with learning disabilities in universities and using various data collection tools.</i></p>

Introduction

Education systems in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia stress the importance of providing equal and fair learning opportunities, regardless of differences and differences between individuals, the interest that the Kingdom offers to individuals with disabilities in general - including those with learning difficulties - has been evident. As a result of the adoption of several legislations and laws of a formal nature approving the system for caring for people with disabilities in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, which guarantees the rights of people with disabilities in several areas, including The field of educational and educational services, which stipulated that they be provided at all stages in a manner commensurate with their abilities and needs, and facilitate the process of their enrollment in them (System for the Care of the Disabled, 2000).

Concerning people with learning difficulties, the percentage of these individuals in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia constitutes 5% of students with disabilities, as the number of students with learning difficulties registered in institutes or centers for learning difficulties in higher education institutions in the Kingdom is 26,225 students (Battal, 2016). Several students with learning disabilities may enroll in university education even though they are not known, and some of them prefer not to disclose their disability; for fear of societal stigma, discrimination, or even marginalization that persons with disabilities may be exposed to (Trimmis & Bessas, 2016).

Students with learning disabilities in university education face more complex challenges than in previous academic stages. Because, at this stage, they are responsible for their learning (Moses, 2018). In addition, the attitudes of faculty members towards students with disabilities in general - including those with learning difficulties - and their willingness to provide academic facilities for them have a significant impact on student's performance and their adaptation at the university level (Lipka et al., 2020). Attitude is a person's emotional state formed based on his beliefs or perceptions regarding a subject or towards certain people, which leads him to respond in a certain way or to do a specific behavior, through which the degree of his rejection or acceptance of this subject or these people becomes clear (Ali, 2011).

The importance of the faculty members' knowledge of learning difficulties lies in the fact that they are a heterogeneous group. Difficulties may vary in degree and type (Youssef et al., 2015); Accordingly, the knowledge of faculty members in universities about the characteristics of students with learning disabilities is essential. Because it contributes to the formation of their attitudes towards them; Therefore, this study revealed the nature of the relationship between the attitudes of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University towards students with learning difficulties and the extent of their knowledge of their characteristics.

The study Problem

The number of students enrolled in university education programs with learning disabilities has increased for decades, but their presence is usually ignored or viewed as a problem; in contrast to that view of students with sensory or physical disabilities as suitable groups for university education, the number of students enrolled in university education programs with learning disabilities has increased for decades. However, their presence is usually ignored or viewed as a problem, in contrast to that view of students with sensory or physical disabilities as suitable groups for university education. Students with learning disabilities have average or higher intelligence and can learn and achieve academic success. However, the challenges associated with their education in general - including university education - are purely understanding and social culture and academic and social environments often fail to meet their needs. The barrier to their enrollment in higher education is not fundamentally related to the student himself; Rather, it results from the inappropriate fit between the learner and the educational environment (Al-Qarni, 2021).

On the other hand, the awareness of faculty members in universities about the characteristics of students with learning disabilities is critical. As it constitutes an essential step in achieving their educational goals, and it also determines their behaviors and their attitudes towards students with learning difficulties, which are important determinants of the quality of higher education experiences for them, and these attitudes are considered necessary for the success of students from this category (Trimmis & Bessas, 2016).

This is consistent with the study of Al-Subaie (2018), which indicated that a lack of awareness and negative attitudes towards people with learning disabilities negatively affect the quality of study and students' experience in university education, Abu Nayyan (2019) confirmed that the low quality of academic life, receiving services, and required accommodations increase the chances of academic dropout. The annual report of the Teachers College, the College of Education in Taif, Umm Al-Qura University, and King Abdulaziz University (2007, as mentioned in Al-Harthy, 2013) stated that the percentage of dropout students with learning disabilities at the undergraduate level in the universities of the Western Region is only about 43.75%. Vogel et al. (2008), referenced in (Hansen, 2013), indicated that the negative attitude of faculty members was the most important barrier to the success of students with disabilities and that improving faculty knowledge of disability and accommodations; led to the improvement of these positions.

This was emphasized by Abed & Shackelford (2020) in an exploratory study aimed at assessing educational support requirements in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The results indicated the need for additional support services for postgraduate students and university students with learning disabilities enrolled in higher education institutions. There is a clear need to improve awareness among faculty members and administrators of the needs of students with learning disabilities at both the undergraduate and postgraduate levels.

Based on the preceding, and given the importance of faculty members knowing the characteristics of forming attitudes towards students with learning disabilities, which in turn contribute to raising the quality of their academic life, The current study came to reveal the relationship between faculty members' knowledge of the characteristics of students with learning disabilities, and their attitudes towards them by answering the following questions:

1. What is the level of attitudes of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University towards students with learning difficulties?
2. What is the level of knowledge of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University about the characteristics of students with learning difficulties?
3. Is there a relationship between faculty members' attitudes at King Abdulaziz University towards students with learning difficulties and their knowledge of their characteristics?

Objectives of the study

The current study seeks to:

1. To identify the level of attitudes of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University towards students with learning difficulties.
2. Identify the level of knowledge of faculty members about the characteristics of students with learning difficulties.
3. To reveal a relationship between faculty members' attitudes at King Abdulaziz University towards students with learning difficulties and their knowledge of their characteristics.

The Study Importance

Theoretical significance

1. The scarcity of studies in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia - within the limits of the knowledge of the two researchers - dealt with the topic of faculty members' attitudes towards the category of students with learning difficulties and its relationship to the extent of their knowledge of their characteristics.

2. Shedding light on a class of students in the university community with its different characteristics, which were not addressed in the research, and studied sufficiently at the university level.
3. Direct researchers to think about other studies on problems facing learning difficulties at the university level.

Applied significance

1. Provide the Department of Special Education and the Center for Persons with Disabilities at the university with information about colleges and departments that need courses and introductory programs for learning difficulties.
2. Providing the field with a tool useful in measuring attitudes towards people with learning disabilities and the degree of knowledge of their characteristics.

The limits of the study

- **Objective limitation:** the relationship between the attitudes of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University towards students with learning difficulties and their knowledge of their characteristics.
- **Time limit:** the academic year 1442-1444 AH.
- **Spatial Limit:** King Abdulaziz University in Jeddah.
- **The human limit:** faculty members and similar associates of King Abdulaziz University.

Study Terms

Learning Disabilities

The Ministry of Education (2020a) defines learning difficulties as:

Learning disabilities

Disturbances in one or more of the basic psychological processes involved in understanding and using written or spoken language, manifested in disorders of listening, thinking, speaking, reading, writing (spelling, articulation, calligraphy), mathematics, which is not due to reasons related to mental, hearing, visual or other types of disability, learning conditions, or family care.

The researchers adopt this definition as a procedural definition of learning difficulties.

Attitudes of faculty members toward students with learning disabilities:

Al-Subaie (2018) defines it as a cognitive, affective-behavioral trend that includes the knowledge and beliefs of faculty members at the university and their willingness to adjust to teaching and examinations and provide support for students with learning difficulties.

The researchers adopt this definition as a procedural definition of faculty members' attitudes.

Faculty Members

The Ministry of Education (2016b) defines faculty members as university affiliates, including professors, associate professors, assistant professors, lecturers, teaching assistants, language teachers, and research assistants.

They are defined procedurally as all those working at King Abdulaziz University in the teaching profession with different academic degrees, including professors, associate professors, assistant professors, lecturers, teaching assistants, language teachers, and research assistants.

Characteristics of people with learning disabilities

Ibrahim (2010) defines it as characteristics related to learning difficulties in various academic subjects, such as learning difficulties in reading, writing, and arithmetic, in addition to the characteristics of the cognitive and social, and emotional domains.

It is defined procedurally as the characteristics of individuals with learning difficulties, which will be included in the questionnaire of knowledge of the characteristics of people with learning disabilities, represented in characteristics of the cognitive domain, characteristics of the social-emotional domain, characteristics of the domain of academic achievement prepared by the two researchers.

Previous Studies

This part reviews the studies that the two researchers found that came close to addressing the current study topic. All studies were arranged based on the historical sequence from the oldest to the most recent and then commented on in terms of points of agreement and disagreement with the current study.

Murray et al. (2008) conducted a survey study to examine the attitudes of faculty members at the University of Oregon and DePaul University towards students with learning disabilities. To achieve this goal, the researchers applied the study tool, which consisted of a questionnaire consisting of four dimensions (knowledge about learning difficulties, readiness to provide adaptations and support, understanding of available

support services, and the need for professional development) on a sample of (70) participants. The results showed positive attitudes toward students with learning difficulties among faculty members, their willingness to provide the necessary adjustments, and the presence of statistically significant differences in favor of female faculty members in the knowledge of learning difficulties. They have positive attitudes and are more willing to provide academic facilities than male members; there are also statistically significant differences between colleges, as faculty members in the College of Education are more willing to provide facilities than colleges of commerce, liberal arts, and sciences. The results indicated that faculty members need training and professional development concerning students with learning disabilities at the undergraduate level and that postsecondary institutions need to provide continuous and recurring opportunities for faculty members; To develop their knowledge about the needs of students with learning difficulties.

As for the study of Al-Thuwaibi (2009) aimed to identify the awareness of faculty members about learning difficulties at the university level, the need of students with learning difficulties for supportive university programs, and the nature of the appropriate environment for them according to scientific specialization, academic rank, and experience, using the survey method. To achieve this goal, the researcher applied the study tool represented by a questionnaire to estimate the need for support programs for students with learning difficulties and what are their requirements for the study sample, which consisted of (280) male faculty members (professor, associate professor, assistant professor). The study results showed that there is awareness among faculty members of the phenomenon of learning difficulties, in addition to the need for supportive programs for people with learning disabilities at the university level from the point of view of the study sample.

The results also showed the need to create an appropriate educational environment for students with learning difficulties and the absence of statistically significant differences in the awareness of faculty members of the phenomenon of learning difficulties according to the different variables: (specialization, academic rank, and experience), in addition to the absence of statistically significant differences in the extent of the need for support programs for people with learning disabilities at the university level from their point of view, according to the difference in specialization.

Hansen's study (2013) aimed to reveal the willingness of faculty members at a community college in Ontario, Canada, to teach students with learning disabilities using a mixed methodology. To achieve this goal, a questionnaire consisting of two main dimensions was applied: (Knowledge of students with learning difficulties and their support and the attitudes of members towards students with learning difficulties), based on a sample of 101 members, and semi-structured interviews with 12 faculty members, it consisted of the following axes: (Members' perceptions of their willingness to teach students with learning difficulties - general myths and misunderstandings about learning difficulties - and a misunderstanding of their characteristics and needs -the discrepancy between the study environment and "real work"--the members' concerns about students' ability, and their willingness to reveal their difficulty). The quantitative and qualitative results showed that the faculty members are not sufficiently prepared to teach students with learning difficulties, despite the presence of general positive attitudes and self-knowledge about learning difficulties to some extent in both the attitudes, knowledge, and knowledge dimensions. It also revealed the importance of informing members about individuals with learning disabilities. The interview results showed the faculty members' general willingness and openness to students with diverse educational needs. Years of experience did not affect knowledge and attitudes.

It also revealed the importance of informing members about individuals with learning disabilities. The interview results showed the faculty members' general willingness and openness to students with diverse educational needs. Years of experience had no effect on knowledge and attitudes, knowledge of learning difficulty, attitudes and facilities for students with learning difficulties) on the sample consisting of (50) faculty members, and the results of the study concluded that the faculty members have positive attitudes toward students with learning difficulties; they are also willing to accommodate them through the adaptations that members use with members of this category, such as: extending the time of exams and projects, in addition to the presence of statistically significant differences in the attitudes towards students with learning difficulties due to the gender variable in favor of females.

As the study of Trimmis and Bessas (2016) aimed to know the attitudes of faculty members regarding the academic success of university students with learning disabilities, on members of a sample consisting of (10) faculty members in three colleges in Greece to achieve this goal, the survey method was used through the application of the study tool represented in a questionnaire to measure the attitudes of university professors and the knowledge of students with learning difficulties. It consisted of the following dimensions: (positive-negative attitudes, the importance of communication with students with learning difficulties, the importance of training members); analysis of the results showed that most university professors believe that students with learning disabilities can be successful at the college level when they are provided with appropriate interventions. It also showed that university professors are not ready for the task of teaching people with learning disabilities enrolled in higher education in Greece, in addition to the need for higher education institutions to provide continuous opportunities for faculty members; to develop their knowledge about the needs of students with learning disabilities; In order to improve their educational and career outcomes.

The study of Talfah and Ammari (2018) aimed to reveal the attitudes of faculty members in the faculties of physical education in Jordanian universities towards accepting students with disabilities within their programs, and the types of disability that can be accepted, and to identify the statistically significant differences between the attitudes of members according to the variables: (type of disability, university, subject teacher (theoretical, practical, theoretical and practical), gender, academic rank, and teaching experience), to achieve this goal, the descriptive approach was used by applying the questionnaire to a sample consisting of (43) members. The results showed that there is a positive trend towards accepting students with disabilities and that most of the disabilities that are accepted among members are hearing disabilities. It also showed that the attitudes of members at the Hashemite University are more positive in accepting people with disabilities than other universities, in addition to the absence of statistically significant differences between the trends of males and females, the nature of the subjects taught, and the academic rank, it also indicated the existence of statistically significant differences according to the teaching experience of the member, in favor of those with more than ten years of experience.

In the same context, Al-Olayani's study (Alalyani, 2021) examined the attitudes of faculty members toward university students with learning difficulties and their willingness to provide academic facilities in a Saudi public university in the Western region, based on the variables: gender, teaching experience, academic rank, and department of the faculty member. The study used the survey method, and the study tool applied, which is the ATDP scale of attitudes towards people with disabilities and a questionnaire of faculty members' attitudes towards facilities for people with learning disabilities. The sample consisted of 261 faculty members from various colleges, and the results confirmed the existence of positive attitudes toward students with learning difficulties. However, some faculty members expressed negative attitudes towards some scale items. The results also showed the readiness of the faculty members to provide appropriate facilities for people with learning difficulties at a rate of 72%, in addition to the absence of a relationship between the attitudes of faculty members towards university students with learning difficulties and their willingness to provide facilities, and the absence of statistically significant differences between the attitudes of faculty members towards students with learning difficulties, and their willingness to provide appropriate facilities according to each of the variables: gender, years of teaching experience, and academic rank.

Alqami's (2021) study dealt with the extent to which faculty members are familiar with the inclusive practices of students with learning disabilities at Najran University using a quantitative survey design. To achieve this goal, the researcher applied the study tool represented by a questionnaire on a sample of 246 faculty members. Differences were noted in the overall practices offered to students, as Saudi faculty members were not sufficiently familiar with teaching practices, classrooms, and assignments. The study also showed that Saudi faculty members were unaware of the testing practices offered to students with learning disabilities.

The study of both Al-Salami and Al-Sharif (2022) sought to identify the administrative, academic, and social services provided to students with learning disabilities in Saudi universities from the point of view of faculty members and specialists using the qualitative approach to achieve this goal; the two researchers applied the study tool (interview) to the study sample, which consisted of four faculty members and three specialists in centers for people with disabilities in Saudi universities. The results showed agreement with the views of the participants about the limited administrative and academic services provided to people with learning disabilities in Saudi universities, in addition to the lack of prior planning for the provision of these services, and that they are not provided to individuals of this category compared to other groups of people with disabilities, it also showed several challenges such as challenges related to service provision, challenges related to students with learning difficulties represented in the lack of awareness of the university community, negative attitudes towards them, and finally challenges related to service centers for students with disabilities.

Commenting on previous studies

By reviewing previous studies, it is possible - to some extent - to identify the research gap that the current study is trying to contribute to covering, as all previous studies dealt with a general goal that is common to the current study; it is related to the opinions, beliefs, and attitudes of faculty members towards students with learning difficulties at the university level. There are several studies concerned with measuring the attitudes of faculty members towards students with learning difficulties, their willingness to teach them, and the provision of academic services and accommodations, as in the study of Murray and Hansen (2008) and the study of Trimmis, Bessas (2016), and the study of Khansa (2015), and the study of Talfah, Ammari (2018), and a group that dealt with knowledge and awareness of students with learning difficulties, the experiences of faculty members, their teaching experiences, their training needs, knowledge of laws for people with disabilities, and the rights of people with learning disabilities, such as the study of Al-Dhoibi (2009) and the study of Alqarni (2021).

The current study agrees with all the studies that were presented previously with the target group, who are faculty members. The previous studies differ in terms of the methodology used, as most of them used the survey method in quantitative studies, except for the study of Talfah and Ammari (2018), which used the descriptive method, while the study of Al-Salami and Al-Sharif (2022) adopted the qualitative approach, while the current study used the descriptive-relational method. In terms of the tool, the current study was similar to

several previous studies in the tool used, which is the questionnaire, such as (Study 2008) Murray and Hansen (2013) and Study Trimmis, Bessas (2016), Khansa (2015), Telfah and Ammari (2018), Alalyani (2021) and Alqarni (2021), except for Al-Sulami and Al-Sharif (2022), which used the interview.

The current study was distinguished from previous studies by knowing the relationship between the attitudes of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University towards students with learning difficulties and the extent of their knowledge of their characteristics, where it agrees with previous studies in its subject and differs in that it added the variable of knowledge of characteristics, and in the place of its application, as it was applied to four colleges at King Abdulaziz University. As far as the two researchers are aware, this study is considered the first one that investigated the attitudes of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University toward students with learning difficulties.

Study Method

The current study relied on the descriptive correlational approach due to its suitability for its objectives and answering its questions. The descriptive approach is the approach that studies the phenomenon as it is in reality and describes it accurately. In contrast, the correlational approach examines the relationships between two or more variables. To find out the extent of the association between these variables, to express them quantitatively, and to determine the type of association (Abbas et al., 2014). The two researchers did this by applying the study tool to the sample. To access information, collect evidence, tabulate data, and extract the results reached, which achieves the study's objectives.

Study population and its sample

The study population consisted of all faculty members at King Abdulaziz University in Jeddah, who numbered (844.5), according to the data received from the Deanship of Information Technology at the university for the academic year 2021/2022.

As for the study sample, it consisted of (122) faculty members at King Abdulaziz University in Jeddah, who were chosen randomly from the study population.

The Study Tool

To achieve the objectives of the study, the study tool, which consisted of a questionnaire, was prepared according to the following steps:

1. Refer to the theoretical framework, previous studies, and relevant references (e.g., Ibrahim, 2010; Abu Nayyan, 2019; Al-Harthy, 2013; Al-Khatib, 2013; Al-Subaie, 2018; Al-Fadhli, 2018; Khansa, 2015; Hansen, 2013; Murray et al., 2008; Trimmis & Bessas, 2016) in order to determine the basic dimensions to be included in the tool, and then review that literature; To derive particular phrases related to each dimension.
 2. Distributing an exploratory questionnaire to six specialists in the field of special education, the course of learning difficulties, as the questionnaire included three open questions, which are:
 - What are the most prominent characteristics of individuals with learning disabilities in the cognitive field?
 - What are the most prominent characteristics of individuals with learning disabilities in the academic field?
 - What are the most prominent characteristics of individuals with learning disabilities in the social and emotional domain?
- With the aim of collecting primary data, surveying the opinions of the study sample, and then emptying the answers to those questions; In order to limit the most prominent characteristics of individuals with learning difficulties, and to benefit from them in formulating the questionnaire statements, in addition to what has been reached from the research in the previous literature.
3. Preparing the initial image of the tool, which consisted of two dimensions; the first dimension consists of (20) paragraphs; To measure the degree of knowledge of the attitudes of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University towards students with learning difficulties by answering according to the triple Likert scale (agree/neutral/disagree) on each of the paragraphs, note that some of the paragraphs bear positive trends, while others carry negative trends. to achieve the desired goal. As for the second dimension, it consists of (27) paragraphs. To measure the knowledge of faculty members about the characteristics of students with learning difficulties by answering "yes or no" to each of the paragraphs, bearing in mind that some of the paragraphs were incorrect. To achieve the desired goal.
 4. Presentation of the study tool in its initial form to a group of specialists in special education.
 5. Making the necessary modifications to the tool according to what was stated by the arbitrators, and taking into account their opinions and directives, and among the amendments included is rearranging the paragraphs logically and sequentially, and amending the wording of some paragraphs, such as paragraphs: (4,3,1,8,15,18) in the first dimension of the tool, and paragraphs: (7,4,1) in the first axis of the second dimension, and paragraphs: (4,3,1) in the second axis of the second dimension, and paragraphs: (9,3,2) in the third axis From the second dimension, and thus the tool became composed in its final form of two dimensions:

The first dimension: Consists of (20) items to measure the degree of knowledge of faculty members' attitudes toward students with learning difficulties.

The second dimension: consists of (27) items to measure the knowledge of faculty members about the characteristics of students with learning difficulties, divided into three axes, which are:

- a. Cognitive Domain: It includes eight paragraphs.
- b. The social-emotional domain: It includes ten paragraphs.
- c. Scope of Academic Achievement: It includes nine paragraphs.

Psychometric characteristics of the study tool:

First - Validity of the tool: The validity of the study tool was confirmed in measuring what it was designed for in the following ways:

- a. **Referee Validity:** In order to know the validity of the study tool in measuring what it was set to measure, the two researchers, to ensure its apparent validity, presented it to ten specialized arbitrators in the Department of Special Education in order to seek their opinions about the appropriateness of each paragraph of the questionnaire to measure what it was designed for, and the extent of its formulation clarity, and the correction of what should be corrected from it, with the addition or deletion of what they see of the paragraphs, and the rates of approval of the arbitrators on the appropriateness of the questionnaire paragraphs and the clarity of their formulation ranged between (80-100%), they are appropriate percentages of agreement, and the two researchers made some adjustments according to the arbitrators' directives and suggestions.
- b. **Internal consistency validity:** To extract the validity of internal consistency (construction validity), the tool was applied to an exploratory sample of (30) faculty members at King Abdulaziz University in Jeddah from the participants in the main sample of the study, the "Person Correlation" coefficient was used to calculate the extent to which each statement relates to the dimension or the axis it represents, and then to calculate the extent to which each dimension relates to the total score of the tool. The results were as shown in the following tables (1), (2), (3), and (4):
 - a. The validity of the internal consistency of the first dimension (attitudes towards students with learning disabilities):

Table 1. The results of the validity of the internal consistency of the statements of the first dimension of the tool

N	Correlation coefficient values	Sig	N	Correlation coefficient values	Sig
1	0.589**	0.01	11	0.648**	0.01
2	0.724**	0.01	12	0.545**	0.01
3	0.589**	0.01	13	0.452**	0.01
4	0.586**	0.01	14	0.705**	0.01
5	0.523**	0.01	15	0.707**	0.01
6	0.586**	0.01	16	0.436**	0.01
7	0.715**	0.01	17	0.728**	0.01
8	0.782**	0.01	18	0.579**	0.01
9	0.647**	0.01	19	0.547**	0.01
10	0.540**	0.01	20	0.551**	0.01

It is clear from Table (1) that the correlation coefficients of the expressions of the first dimension of the tool (attitudes towards students with learning difficulties) with the total score of the tool ranged between (0.436-0.782). They were all statistically significant at the significance level (0.01), this confirms that all statements of the first dimension of the tool have a high degree of internal validity.

b. The validity of the internal consistency of the second dimension (characteristics of students with learning disabilities):

Table 2. The validity of the internal consistency of the first axis of the second dimension (characteristics of the cognitive domain)

N	Correlation coefficient values	Sig	N	Correlation coefficient values	Sig
1	0.589**	0.01	5	0.696**	0.01
2	0.752**	0.01	6	0.666**	0.01
3	0.596**	0.01	7	0.715**	0.01
4	0.758**	0.01	8	0.725**	0.01

It is clear from Table (2) that the correlation coefficients of the phrases of the first axis of the second dimension (characteristics of the cognitive field) with the total score of the axis ranged between (0.589-0.758). They were all statistically significant at the level of significance (0.01), this confirms that all the statements of the first axis of the second dimension have a high degree of internal validity.

Table 3. The validity of the internal consistency of the second axis of the second dimension (the social-emotional domain)

N	Correlation coefficient values	Sig	N	Correlation coefficient values	Sig
1	**0.706	0.01	6	**0.756	0.01
2	**0.724	0.01	7	**0.704	0.01
3	**0.715	0.01	8	**0.745	0.01
4	**0.697	0.01	9	**0.723	0.01
5	**0.658	0.01	10	**0.540	0.01

By reviewing the results shown in Table (3), it is clear that the correlation coefficients of the phrases of the second axis of the second dimension (the social-emotional domain) with the total score of the axis ranged between (0.540-0.756), all of them were statistically significant at the significance level (0.01), which confirms that all statements of the second axis of the second dimension have a high degree of internal validity.

Table 4. The validity of the internal consistency of the third axis of the second dimension (the domain of academic achievement)

N	Correlation coefficient values	Sig	N	Correlation coefficient values	Sig
1	**0.697	0.01	6	**0.750	0.01
2	**0.756	0.01	7	**0.751	0.01
3	**0.753	0.01	8	**0.757	0.01
4	**0.586	0.01	9	**0.741	0.01
5	**0.523	0.01	-	-	-

*** Statistically significant at the level of significance (0.01).*

The results shown in Table (4) indicate that the correlation coefficients of the phrases of the third axis of the second dimension (the field of academic achievement) with the total score of the axis ranged between (0.523-0.757), all of them were statistically significant at the significance level (0.01), which confirms that all statements of the third axis of the second dimension have a high degree of internal validity.

Second – Reliability of the tool: The reliability of the study tool was confirmed by applying the Cronbach-Alpha equation, and the results appeared as in Table (5):

Table 5. The reliability coefficient of the study tool

N	The study tool and its dimensions	Cronbach coefficient	alpha
	The first dimension: Attitudes toward students with learning difficulties.	0.869	
	The second dimension: the characteristics of students with learning difficulties.	0.896	
1	The first axis: the cognitive domain	0.879	
2	The second axis: the emotional, social domain	0.881	
3	The third axis: the field of academic achievement	0.853	
	The total items of the study tool	0.902	

By reviewing the results shown in Table (5), it is clear that the values of the stability coefficient for the dimensions of the resolution and its axes ranged between (0.853-0.896), which are high values. The general stability of the tool was (0.902); This indicates that the tool has a high degree of stability, and therefore it can be relied upon in the field application of the study.

The method of correcting the tool and the criterion for judging the degree of approval:

- a. To correct the first dimension of the tool: The answer (agree) was given 3 degrees, and the answer (neutral) was 2 degrees, while the answer (not agreeing) was given 1 degree, and then the two researchers calculated the arithmetic mean of the sample's answers, The length of the cells of the triangular scale (lower and upper limits) used in the axes of the study was determined, where the range (3-1=2) was calculated, then divided by the number of cells of the scale; To get the correct cell length, i.e.: (2/3=0.66), then this value is added to the lowest value in the scale (or the

beginning of the scale which is the integer); This is to determine the upper limit of this cell, and thus the length of the cells became as shown in Table (6):

Table 6. Degree of approval and extent of approval

Degree of approval	Coding	Extent of approval	Level
Disagree	1	From 1 to 1.66	Low
Neutral	2	From 1.67 to 2.33	Medium
Agree	3	From 2.34 to 3	High

- b. To correct the second dimension of the tool: The answer (yes) was given two degrees, and the answer (no) one degree. The two researchers calculated the arithmetic mean of the sample answers. The length of the binary scale cells (lower and upper limits) used in the study axes was determined, where the range (2-1=1) was calculated, then divided by the number of cells of the scale; To get the correct cell length, i.e.: (1/2 = 0.50), then this value was added to the lowest value in the scale (or the beginning of the scale, which is the correct one); This is to determine the upper limit of this cell, and thus the length of the cells became as shown in Table (7):

Table 7. Degree of approval and extent of approval

Degree of approval	Coding	Degree of approval	Level
No	1	From 1-1.50	Low
Yes	2	1.51-2	High

Study procedures

After preparing the study tool in the final form, the two researchers completed the necessary procedures to distribute it to the study sample according to the following steps:

1. Determine the study population and sample.
2. Obtain an assignment facilitation letter from the Graduate School to facilitate the procedures for applying the questionnaire.
3. The questionnaire was distributed electronically through the Research Services Unit to the study population of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University in Jeddah in the first semester of the year (1443 AH), and the application lasted four months.
4. Sort and emptying questionnaires.
5. Analyze the data using appropriate statistical processing.

Statistical treatment

To serve the purposes of the study and to analyze the data collected, the two researchers used several statistical methods using the Statistical Analysis Program for Social Sciences (SPSS-v25) as follows:

1. The Cronbach alpha coefficient for calculating the stability values of the resolution and its axes.
2. Pearson correlation coefficient to calculate the internal consistency of the questionnaire items.
3. Analyze the questionnaire using frequencies and percentages to identify the personal and functional characteristics of the study sample and determine the responses towards the paragraphs of the axes included in the questionnaire.
4. Arithmetic means, standard deviations, and ranks; To find out the general trend of the paragraphs and axes of the questionnaire.
5. Pearson correlation coefficients; To calculate the relationship between the level of attitudes of faculty members and their level of knowledge of the characteristics of students with learning difficulties.

The Study Results

The following is a detailed presentation of the results of the study by answering its questions:

Results related to answering the first question: "What is the level of attitudes of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University towards students with learning difficulties?", In order to answer this question, the arithmetic means, and standard deviations were extracted for the level of attitudes of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University towards students with learning difficulties, where this axis included (20) paragraphs that measure the level of attitudes of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University towards students with learning difficulties, and Table (8) shows this.

Table 8. Arithmetic means and standard deviations for the level of attitudes of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University towards students with learning disabilities

N	Items	Mean	STD	Practice degree	Ranking
5	I encourage students with learning difficulties to	2.88	0.34	High	1

N	Items	Mean	STD	Practice degree	Ranking
	benefit from the university services provided to them.				
16	I want more information about the needs of students with learning disabilities.	2.87	0.39	High	2
3	Students with learning disabilities have multiple talents.	2.85	0.37	High	3
7	I agree that students with learning disabilities should record the lectures.	2.83	0.46	High	4
19	I provide facilities for students with learning difficulties if they are consistent with the integrity of my courses.	2.82	0.47	High	5
18	I use technology; To improve the performance of students with learning difficulties.	2.81	0.43	High	6
17	Providing facilities for students with learning disabilities ensures their equal opportunities with others and their success.	2.80	0.47	High	7
10	Students with learning disabilities do well at the university level.	2.68	0.50	High	8
8	I seek assistance from the Center for People with Special Needs when teaching students with learning difficulties.	2.53	0.67	High	9
9	I am interested in attending training courses on learning difficulties.	2.49	0.74	High	10
14	I lack sufficient knowledge to ensure fair educational opportunities for people with learning disabilities.	2.34	0.77	High	11
4	Students with learning disabilities attribute their poor performance to their disability.	2.13	0.77	Moderate	12
2	I consider vocational training programs the most suitable option for students with learning disabilities.	1.94	0.88	Moderate	13
1	Students with learning disabilities have below-average mental abilities.	1.69	0.82	Moderate	14
11	I consider adapting tests for students with learning disabilities to be unfair to other students.	1.68	0.72	Moderate	15
15	As a faculty member, I am burdened when I demand accommodations for people with learning disabilities.	1.64	0.83	Moderate	16
6	The presence of students with learning disabilities reduces the quality of education for the rest of the students.	1.40	0.71	Low	17
13	Providing facilities for students with learning difficulties is optional of faculty members.	1.35	0.66	Low	18
20	Providing facilities for students with learning difficulties in higher education wastes time.	1.26	0.61	Low	19
12	I consider learning disabilities a "myth" that does not exist.	1.18	0.53	Low	20
The tool as a whole		2.21	0.19	Moderate	

Table (8) shows the arithmetic means, standard deviations, and rank for each paragraph of the tool for the attitudes of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University towards students with learning disabilities and the dimension as a whole. It is noted that the arithmetic averages for this tool ranged between (1.18-2.88) with a high degree of practice for (11 items), a medium degree of practice for (5 items), and a low degree of practice for (4 items). As for the dimension, it obtained an arithmetic average of (2.21), representing a medium degree of

practice.

Item No. (5) ranked first, which reads: "I encourage students with learning difficulties to benefit from the university services provided to them," with an arithmetic mean (2.88), and a standard deviation (0.34), with a high degree of practice. Paragraph No. (16) came in second place, which reads: "I would like to obtain more information regarding the needs of students with learning difficulties," with an arithmetic mean (2.87) and a standard deviation (0.37), with a high degree of practice.

Paragraph No. (20) came the penultimate, which reads: "Providing facilities for students with learning difficulties in higher education is a waste of time," with an arithmetic mean (1.26) and a standard deviation (0.61), with a low degree of practice. Whereas, Paragraph No. (12) came in last place, which reads: "I consider learning difficulties a "myth" that does not exist in reality, with an arithmetic mean (1.18) and a standard deviation (0.53), with a low degree of practice.

Concerning the overall score for the Attitudes dimension (which is an average of 2.21 out of 3); It can be said: This average expresses an average state in general, as it did not approach 3 (which agrees). However, we also note that the average exceeded the "2" by (0.21); This indicates a slight tendency for the participants to agree on the positive attitude towards dealing with students with learning difficulties. In other words, those with a high score (close to 3) are slightly more numerous than those with a low score (close to 1). The matter could be more straightforward if the scale were five (instead of three), as participants' general tendency would be broken down into five scales and given a slight tendency towards agreement (i.e., average being slightly higher than '2').

The two researchers refer this result to the interest of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University in creating an appropriate educational environment that allows equal opportunities between students with learning disabilities and their peers, and their appreciation for individual differences among students in general, and students with learning difficulties in particular, and because they have sufficient experience in dealing with different categories of students, and this may be due to King Abdulaziz University providing special academic services that help students with learning difficulties, and contribute to increasing their academic competence; This helps raise faculty members' awareness of the importance of obtaining more information about the needs of students with learning difficulties, which would increase their experience in how to deal with these students, and awareness of their rights, and then improve their attitudes and increase their acceptance of members of this category.

This is consistent with the results of other studies that showed positive attitudes of the teaching staff towards students with learning difficulties, such as the results of the study of Murray et al. (Murray et al., 2008), which indicated that there are positive attitudes of the study sample of faculty members towards students with learning disabilities, and their willingness to provide services and accommodations, and the study of Khansa (2015), which concluded that the study sample had positive attitudes towards students with learning difficulties, and the study of Talfah and Ammari (2018), which revealed positive attitudes of faculty members at the Hashemite University towards accepting people with disabilities, and agreed with the result of Al-Olayani's study (Alalyani, 2021), which confirmed the existence of positive attitudes among faculty members towards students with learning difficulties, while it differs with the result of the study of Trimmis & Bessas (Trimmis & Bessas, 2016), which revealed the lack of readiness of the study sample for the task of teaching people with learning disabilities, Moreover, Alqarni's (2021) study, which found apparent differences in the inclusive practices offered to students with learning disabilities.

Results related to the second question: "What is the level of knowledge of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University about the characteristics of students with learning difficulties?" In order to answer this question, the arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for the level of knowledge of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University about the characteristics of students with learning disabilities, and Table (9) shows this.

Table 9. Means and standard deviations of the axes of the level of knowledge of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University about the characteristics of students with learning disabilities, arranged in descending order

	The main axes	ean	TD	Knowledge degree	R anking
	characteristics of the cognitive domain	.64	.22	High	1

Domain characteristics of academic achievement	.60	.19	High	2
Characteristics of the Emotional, social Domain	.57	.20	High	3
The tool	.60	.16	High	

Table No. (9) shows the levels of viewpoints of the study sample about the level of knowledge of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University about the characteristics of students with learning disabilities; this is done by calculating the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the axes of the second dimension of the tool, which is related to the level of knowledge of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University about the characteristics of students with learning difficulties for each axis separately, and then arranging the axes, as the averages ranged between (1.57-1.64). This indicates a high level of knowledge.

Accordingly, the results of this question revealed that the level of knowledge of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University about the characteristics of students with learning difficulties was "high" on the total score. On all aspects, the characteristics of the cognitive domain came in the first rank of the tool axes, with a high degree of knowledge. The second rank of the tool axes came in the characteristics of the academic achievement domain, with a high degree of knowledge. The third and last rank of the tool axes came in the characteristics of the social-emotional domain, with a high degree of knowledge.

The researchers attribute this result to the spread of communication channels between specialists in the field of learning difficulties and university faculty members, in addition to conferences, seminars, lectures, or workshops held continuously and periodically in this field. This contributes directly and effectively to raising faculty members' awareness of the characteristics of students with learning difficulties.

This result is consistent with the result of Al-Thuwaibi's (2009) study, which showed awareness among the study sample of faculty members of the phenomenon of learning difficulties, while this result differed with the results of the study of Al-Salami and Al-Sharif (2022), which revealed that among the challenges facing people with learning disabilities (from the perspective of specialized faculty members) is the lack of awareness of the university community about them, and the inability to know their characteristics, and the study of Hansen (2013) which showed that the study sample was not adequately prepared for the task of teaching students with learning difficulties.

Results related to the third question: "Is there a relationship between the attitudes of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University towards students with learning difficulties and their knowledge of the characteristics of learning difficulties?" to answer this question, Pearson's correlation coefficient was calculated between the level of faculty members' attitudes and the sub-dimensions of their level of knowledge of the characteristics of students with learning disabilities. Table (10) shows this.

Table 10. Pearson correlation coefficients between the level of attitudes of faculty members and their level of knowledge of the characteristics of students with learning disabilities

	Sub-themes of the characteristics of students with learning difficulties			
	characteristics of the cognitive domain	Characteristics of the Emotional, Social Domain	Characteristics of the Field of academic achievement	The total score for their level of knowledge of the characteristics of students with learning disabilities
The level of attitudes of faculty members	*0.809	*0.715	*0.759	*0.842

*Significant at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

Table No. (10) shows that there is a strong, direct, linear correlation (by Pearson coefficient) with a solid statistical significance at the level of significance (0.05) between the level of attitudes of faculty members, and the axes of their level of knowledge of the characteristics of students with learning disabilities, the value of the correlation coefficient was not less than (0.75) in all axes, and the significance was ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in all coefficients. All coefficients for correlation are considered high, as they are close to 1 (which is the extreme limit of correlation), Which indicates a strong relationship between trends and knowledge of characteristics.

This confirms the extent of compatibility and correlation between faculty members' attitudes and the dimensions of their level of knowledge of the characteristics of students with learning difficulties. The two researchers believe it is a logical link, as the individual's orientation depends mainly on the knowledge he receives. In the case of the current study, the more information a faculty member has about a particular class of students, it is natural that he will have more understanding of the student's problem and the tendency to provide appropriate support. This result can also be explained by the conditions of King Abdulaziz University for the teaching staff, which include the need for faculty members to complete their higher education in prestigious

universities. Thus, they may have been exposed to the necessity of providing equal educational opportunities for all students, including those with learning difficulties, and providing them with academic services and facilities. To ensure that they have equal education opportunities and participate fully in university life. This is in addition to the fact that during their bachelor's, Master's, and doctoral studies, they may have associated with some individuals with disabilities and succeeded in providing the academic services they need.

This result does not agree or differ with any of the previous studies, which is what distinguishes the current study in that it is the first study - as far as the two researchers know - that searched for the relationship between the attitudes of faculty members at King Abdulaziz University towards students with learning difficulties and their knowledge of the characteristics of learning difficulties.

Study Recommendations

In light of the findings of the current study, some recommendations can be made:

1. Research using multiple variables such as the source of knowledge about people with learning disabilities and gender.
2. Conduct qualitative studies on attitudes toward people with learning disabilities in universities using various data collection tools.

Suggested research:

Proposals to enrich research in the field of learning difficulties in university education:

- Faculty members' attitudes towards students with learning disabilities at King Abdulaziz University: a qualitative study.
- Improving the Academic Services Provided to Students with Learning Disabilities in Saudi Universities: A Proposed Concept.
- Challenges facing students with learning disabilities at King Abdulaziz University.

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